

FEASIBILITY OF OPENING NON-FORMAL SCHOOLS IN AFGHANISTAN: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

The literacy rate in Afghanistan is not satisfactory throughout the ages. Currently, a large portion (around 4 million) of the school-age-children are out-of-schools in the country (UNICEF, 2021). The study aimed to investigate the feasibility of opening non-formal schools to enrol out-of-school children and alleviate illiteracy in Kunar province of Afghanistan. The objectives of the study were: i) to investigate the educational accessibility gap in Kunar Province, ii) to assess the need for opening non-formal schools in Kunar Province, and iii) to explore potential strategies for opening non-formal schools in Kunar Province. A case study, qualitative research design was used for the study. The population of the study included officials from education sector, headmasters, teachers, Mosque Imams, and parents in Kunar province. 62 participants were purposively selected as the sample of the study. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews and was analysed using thematic analysis. The study found that opening non-formal schools in Kunar Province of Afghanistan are feasible because there is an educational accessibility gap and positive attitudes towards opening non-formal schools. Moreover, Mosques, guesthouses and formal schools at the evening shift were indicated some of the possible ways to establish non-formal schools in Kunar Province of Afghanistan.

Keywords: Feasibility, Non-Formal Schools, Afghanistan, Kunar Province.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the basic right of every individual. Looking to this fundamental right, the government of Afghanistan and international agencies have exerted all their efforts to educate individuals especially children and help in eradicating illiteracy from Afghanistan. However, with all the efforts, unfortunately the literacy rate in the country is still below the halfway around. Overall, the literacy rate of the country is just around 40% (UNICEF, 2021; UIL, 2020; CSRS, 2019). Moreover, the threatening fact is that a large portion of the school age children (around 4 million children) are out-of-school in the country (UNICEF, 2021; Rescue.org, 2021; Beteille et al., 2020; World Bank Report, 2020; REUTERS, 2018).

The causes that result in keeping children out-of-school in the country are many. To mention some of the main causes identified by several studies are decades of political tensions and civil wars in the country, poverty, low economy of the country, shortage of schools, shortage of schools infrastructures, cultural norms, illiteracy of parents and lack

of security in the country, (Kerawala, 2021; Menteş & Talas, 2021; Daud, 2020; Mashwani, 2017; Noori, 2017; Khwajamir, 2016; EFA, 2015).

In such condition where besides other numerous hurdles, poverty, low economy of the country and shortage of formal schools (FSs) are the main obstacles in the way of child education; Non-Formal Schools (NFSs) in the form of Mosque Schools (MSs), existing FSs buildings as Evening Schools (ESs) and guesthouses in the community could be the solution. NFSs are cost-effective and have been proven effective in supporting formal schools in the provision of basic education. They are effective for its diversity and flexibility in conditions where children could not make to formal schools due to various obstacles (Gul & Sarwar, 2020). If the government's low economy does not allow for establishing sufficient number of FSs, it could support opening NFSs i.e., MSs and schools in the guesthouses of the community to educate the educationally marginalised children. Furthermore, the existing FSs at the Evening shift (ESs) may be opened for those children who work in the labour market at daytime to financially support their families.

The focus of the current study is to investigate the feasibility of opening NFSs (MSs, ESs and schools in the guesthouses of the community) to alleviate illiteracy in Afghanistan. The issue and situation in majority of the provinces of the country are the same; so, the current study is delimited to only one province i.e., Kunar Province of Afghanistan. The study specifically tries to investigate the educational accessibility gap in Kunar Province, to assess the need for opening non-formal schools in Kunar Province, and to explore viable strategies for opening non-formal schools in Kunar Province of Afghanistan.

Research Objectives

- i) To investigate the educational accessibility gap in Kunar Province
- ii) To assess the need for non-formal schools in Kunar Province
- iii) To explore potential strategies for opening non-formal schools in Kunar Province

LITERATURE REVIEW

NFSs also termed as second chance schools are educational institutions that are flexible in their method of delivering education and usually aimed at providing education to the educationally marginalised group of the society. These are alternative institutions that help FSs in the provision of basic education for those who are vulnerable and inaccessible. These educational institutions are relatively similar to FSs in delivering basic education, but they differs in the organization, financing, study programs, operating environment, staffing conditions and the group of students they focus on (Nyaga, 2016; Kaugi, 2015; Ruto, 2004). In short, NFSs are institutions that are second chance or alternative schools for those who are side-lined and not covered by the main streamed or first chance schools i.e., formal school system.

Feasibility of Non-Formal Schools

Feasibility is to see whether a project is practical or not. Feasibility study is to see the practicality and viability of an idea (Wright, 2020; Southwood, 2018; Bowen et al., 2009). Studies have revealed positive results on the feasibility of NFSs for the alleviation of illiteracy especially in developing countries (Gull, 2018; Hamid, 2016). Similarly, a number of studies in Bangladesh have proven the feasibility and effectiveness of NFSs in educating millions of children who were deprived from education in FSs (Ibrahim, 2002; Hossain, 1999; Alamgir, 1999). Likewise, community learning centres (TBM) were effectively established in Indonesia that have helped in improving the literacy rate in the community and that was an effective initiative of illiteracy eradication in the country (Afriani, 2019). In summary, NFSs are feasible and have yielded positive results in the alleviation of illiteracy in developing countries.

Out-of-School Children in Kunar Province

The exact number of out-of-schools children is missing; however, Sharma and Afzali (2018) estimate that around 88 thousands of the total school age children are still out-of-schools. Furthermore, KDoE (2022) states that around 63 thousands (26%) of the school-age-children are still out-of-schools in Kunar Province.

Formal Schools in Kunar Province

Due to the weak economy of the country; the government of Afghanistan is not in the position to provide the required number of FSs around the country. The country education sector is heavily dependent on the assistance of international organization to support FSs in providing educational opportunities in hard to access areas of the country (UNICEF, 2019). Currently, around 500 FSs operate in Kunar Province (Sharma & Afzali, 2018). This is supported by KDoE (2022), who states that there are overall 461 (241 public and 20 private) schools in Kunar province. Of the total number of schools (461), there are 241 primary schools, 98 are middle schools and 122 are high schools.

The Use of Mosque as a Non-Formal School

The role of Mosque for the provision of education cannot be ignored. According to Yin et al., (2015) in early days, learning and teaching mostly happened in the Mosques and the first Mosque that acted as an elementary school was almost in 653 AD in Medina. Haider (2021) further stress on the cooperation between schools and Mosques to attain quality in education especially Islamic education. Children who attend Mosques and get religious education in the Mosques have also performed better in literacy tests and have helped them in academic success (Burde et al., 2015). They further state that in a country like Afghanistan where 75% of the population live in rural community and the FE struggles in the provision of basic education in rural areas, MSs are essential. Similarly, Saeed et al., (2016) assert that MSs are the best alternate choice for the provision of basic education in developing countries.

Evening Schools (ESs)

FSs can be opened at the evening shift as ESs for the provision of primary education to those children who work at labour market at daytime. ESs are aimed at providing education to those who have free time in the evening. These schools are flexible and hence effective in the provision of education to those who work at daytime (Jain, 2018; Luka et al., 2015). ESs are also termed as second chance schools that aimed at educating those who go to work at daytime to support their daily expenses (Brinia & Ntaflou, 2015). According to UNICEF (2018), around 2.5 million children (ages 6-14) in Afghanistan are working in the labour market. So, to cater to the issue and provide those 2.5 million children with the opportunity of education, FSs as ESs could be the solution.

Role of Community in Establishing Non-Formal Schools

The role of community cannot be ignored in the success of any community program especially a program that is in search of possible cost-effective solutions to the issue of illiteracy which is the root cause of many other issues for the community. This is what stated by Kedrayate (2001) who says that the active role of the community helps in running a program effectively and helps in the reduction of the cost of the program. Most of the NFSs are run in the form of Community Schools (CSs) which are run in the community for the community and by the community (Rahma et al., 2019). This is what that indicates the importance and the role of community in establishing and supporting NFSs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology being used for the current study. Research setting, research design, population of the study, sample of the study, research instrument and data collection are the main areas being covered in the section.

Research Setting

The study was carried in the Kunar province of Afghanistan. The province has 15 districts and Asadabad is its provincial capital (Sharma & Afzali, 2018). Kunar province is located at the northeast part of Afghanistan. The area of Kunar province is about 4339 km of which 96% of the area is mountainous or semi mountainous. It has a population of around 0.5 million people by 2022. It is the province where the well-known Afghan scholar Allama Sayed Jamaluddin Afghani was born. There is one provincial education directorate and 15 district education directorates at the province. The province has 461 formal public and private schools (241 primary school, 98 middles schools and 102 high schools) where around 4000 teachers currently teach 184256 male and female students (KDoE, 2022). Similarly, the province has 2175 Mosques and so is the number of Imams in the province (KDoHIA, 2022).

Research Design

In order to collect detailed and in-depth data, the researcher used qualitative case study research design for the study. Qualitative research design focuses on in-depth

understanding of a social phenomenon and behaviour in a very naturalistic and contextualized way. The practitioners of qualitative method research argue that the use of qualitative method provides the researcher with a complete and in-depth understanding of the research problem (Fraenkel et al., 2016). As the study is an investigation of the feasibility of opening NFSs to alleviate illiteracy in Kunar Province; a case study approach was used. Case study approach is a qualitative approach in which the researcher studies a real-life case in an in-depth manner usually through observation, interviews, documents, and reports (Creswell, 2013).

Population of the Study

Population is the entire set of items (individuals, objects, events, organization, etc.) to which the outcome of the research may be generalised (Frankel & Wallen, 2016). The aim in qualitative research is not generalisation; however, from the findings of the sample, we can have insights regarding the population. The population of the study included: officials from Directorate of Education (DoE), officials from Directorate of Hajj and Islamic Affairs (DoHIA), headmasters, teachers, Mosque Imams, and parents in Kunar province.

Sample of the Study

Sample is a subset of the population. In a research study sample is the group of individuals, objects, events, organization, etc. on which the data is obtained (Frankel & Wallen, 2016). In general, a sample size in qualitative study should not be too small that it is difficult to achieve saturation and should not be too large that it is difficult to make in-depth analysis (Onwuegbuzie & Collins, 2007). The sample of the study included: the provincial Director of Education, the provincial Director of Hajj and Islamic Affairs, the district DoE, the district DoHIA, a Mosque Imam, a headmaster, a teacher, and a parent at 10 districts of Kunar Province. So, overall, 62 participant were purposively selected as the sample of study. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique in which the researcher decides the sample based on some criteria such as experience or ability (Thomas, 2022). The participants of the study were purposively selected based on their experience and suitability inured to collect pertinent data.

Research Instrument

In order to get in-depth data, semi structured interviews as a data collection instrument was used. Semi-structured interviews are considered more formalized and flexible interviews. The advantage of semi-structured interviews are that they are neither too rigid nor too open and allow the researcher to add additional important questions to them during the interview session (Abd Gani et al., 2020). Based on the various aspect of the current study, the interview items were clearly developed and arranged so that to collect pertinent data that could fully answer research objectives/questions.

Data Collection

Data was collected through semi-structured interviews. A semi-structured interviews with probes and prompts were used to explore the insights of the participants on the subject. For the convenience of the participants, the interview items were translated into their

native language i.e., Pashto language. The data collection procedure started with collecting the data from provincial DoE and provincial DoHIA. Next, the researcher collected data at the district level from 10 DoE, 10 DoHIA, 10 Mosque Imams, 10 headmasters, 10 teachers and 10 parents. Once the data was collected in Pashto language form all the sample thorough voice recorder in a smart phone then the data was transcribed and translated into English language.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data being collected through semi-structured interviews were thematically analysed and interpreted. The data was analysed following the six steps proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006) for the thematic analysis i.e., familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, naming themes, and producing the report. The names of all these participants were kept anonymous and they were assigned pseudonyms. The Provincial Director of Education and the Provincial Director of Hajj and Islamic affairs have been represented as PD1 and PD2. The ten District Directors of Education have been represented as DDE1, DDE2, DDE3 and so on. Likewise, the ten District Directors of Hajj and Islamic affairs have been represented as DDHIA1, DDHIA2, DDHIA3 and so on. Similarly, the ten Headmasters have been represented as HM1, HM2, HM3 and so on. Moreover, the ten Teachers have been represented as T1, T2, T3 and so on. Furthermore, the ten Mosque Imams have been represented as MI1, MI2, MI3 and so on. And the ten Parents have been represented as P1, P2, P3 and so on.

Data Analysis Related to Objective No. 1: Educational Accessibility Gap

Based on the first objective of the study i.e., to investigate the educational accessibility gap in Kunar province, the following main and sub-themes emerged from the analysis of the data as summarised in figure 1.

Figure 1: Themes and Sub-Themes Based on Objective No. 1

Theme No. 1: Insufficient Number of Formal Schools

This theme represents the deficiency of FSs in Kunar province and affirms the feasibility of NFSs in Kunar province. Almost all the participants reported that the current number of FSs is not sufficient for the existing number of school-age-children in Kunar province. They have presented various arguments in support of their standpoint. This is elaborated as follow:

PD1 reported as:

“The schools established so far in Kunar province could not fulfil the needs. They are not sufficient. We have many areas where there is no school...”

DDE7 commented as:

“No, the existing formal primary schools in the district are not sufficient. They have not covered all the school-age-children in the district”

T2 said:

“Well, the current number of formal primary schools is not enough for the school-age-children in the locality. Because there are some areas in the district where there are no formal schools at all”

Moreover, two sub-themes i.e., *Hard to Access Areas* and *Government Limited Resources* emerged in the views of the participants as they pointed out various reasons for the insufficiency of primary schools in the area. These sub-themes are elaborated in the views of participants next.

HM6 stated as:

“The current number of formal primary schools is not adequate because there are many hard to access areas where there are no schools...”

DDE5 argued as:

“I think one of the main reasons that the children are deprived of schools in the district is the limited resources of the government...”

Theme No. 2: Large Number of Out-of-School Children

This theme indicates that a large portion of the school-age-children are out-of-schools in the province. This necessitates the establishment of NFSs and confirms the feasibility of NFSs in the province. Majority of the participants stated that large number of children are out-of-schools in the province. The following stances of the participants elaborate the theme.

PD1 declared as:

“We did a survey about one and a half or two years ago; and we have found that around 30,000 to 35,000 of our children are still out of schools. They do not have access to schools, and they are out-of-schools”

HM3 reported as:

“I do not have the exact information about the number of out-of-schools children in the district, but I can say that around 50% of the school age children are still out-of-schools in the district”

Moreover, several subthemes i.e., *Education Desert, Formal Schools’ Limited Resources, Parents’ Financial Problems and Barriers in the Way to Schools* were being identified by the participants as the main reasons that cause the children to be out-of-schools. These reasons are further elaborated in the stand points of the participants as follow.

DDE1 expressed as:

“The main reason that causes children out-of-schools in the district is the absence of nearby schools. The schools are distantly located from one another”

MI6 shared his point of view as:

“One of the reasons that the children are out-of-schools in the area is that the existing formal schools here in the district do not have sufficient resources...”

P2 elaborated as:

“The schools are far away, and we could not afford to arrange transport for them to carry them to the schools”

T1 reported as:

“Well, the district has very wide canyons. The children of the district could not access the existing formal schools in the district due to numerous obstacles in the way to school such as busy roads, watercourses and mountains...”

Data Analysis Related to Objective No. 2: Need for Opening Non-Formal Schools

Based on the second objective of the study i.e., to assess the need for opening Non-Formal Schools in Kunar province, the following main and sub-themes emerged from the analysis of the data as depicted in figure 2.

Figure 2: Themes and Sub-Themes Based on Objective No. 2

Theme No. 1: Need for the Establishment of Non-Formal Schools

This theme reveals that there is a great need for the establishment of NFSs in the province. This approve the feasibility of NFSs in the province. Most of the participants expressed that the current number of FSs in the province could not fulfil the requirements and there is a need to establish NFSs in the proximity of every village so that to provide the out-of-schools children with the opportunity to come into schools. Some of the comments regarding this theme are as follow:

PD1 affirmed as:

“Yes, there is a great need to build non-formal schools in Kunar province. Our children do not have access to formal schools...”

MI7 shared:

“Truly speaking, there is a need for non-formal schools in our locality. Because there are some children who do not have access to formal schools...”

Moreover, two sub-themes i.e., *Effectiveness of Non-Formal Schooling* and *Parents' Positive attitudes* were emerged in the views of the participants. These sub-themes are elaborated in the comments of the participants as follow.

DDHIA8 elaborated as:

“As far I have noticed, the non-formal schools are very effective. The reason is that they are cost effective and could be established at every village...”

P2 expressed as:

“We will definitely allow our children to non-formal schools if they could be established in near distance...”

Data Analysis Related to Objective No. 3: Potential Strategies for Opening Non-Formal Schools

Based on the third objective of the study i.e., to explore the potential strategies of opening Non-Formal Schools in Kunar province, the following main and sub-themes emerged from the analysis of the data as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Themes and Sub-Themes Based on Objective No. 3

Theme No. 1: Ways of Establishing Non-Formal Schools

This theme indicates that there are several ways of establishing NFSs in the province and makes a positive statement about the feasibility of the NFSs in the province. The participant suggested various suitable strategies for establishing the NFSs. They asserted that *Mosque*, *Guesthouses* and FSs in the evening shift as *Evening Schools* are the potential strategies that may be used for establishing the NFSs in Kunar Province. The following are some of their quotes that elaborate the main and sub-themes.

DDHIA10 suggested as:

“Well, in the past Mosques have been used as non-formal schools because there were no formal schools.... Why not, Mosque can be used as non-formal schools”

DDE8 elaborated as:

“The guesthouses are the suitable places for establishing non-formal schools in as they have the essential facilities required for these schools. The people are also very cooperative, and I am sure they will happily cooperate in this regard...”

HM9 stated as:

“Due to poverty, around sixty percent of the children go to mountains for woods or do other works instead of going to schools.... So, if the formal schools could be opened in the evening shift for such children, this will be a great move to bring in the out-of-school children into schools”

Findings

The findings of the study revealed that NFSs are feasible in Kunar province of Afghanistan because there is an educational accessibility gap i.e., the current number of FSs in Kunar province are not enough and great number of school-age-children are out-of-schools. Hard to access areas and limited resources of the government have resulted the current number of FSs insufficient in the province. Similarly, absence of FSs in near distance, limited resources of the FSs, parents' financial issues and obstacles in the way of children to schools were some of the main reasons that resulted the children out-of-school in Kunar province.

Similarly, the findings of the study indicated that there is a great need for opening NFSs in the province. The current number of FSs in the province may not fulfil the requirements and there is a need to establish NFSs in the proximity of every village. The findings elaborated that establishing NFSs in the province are essential because they are cost-effective compared to the FSs. Similarly, the findings indicated that the parents had positive attitudes towards opening the NFSs in the province. They regarded these NFSs as the need of the day and they promised that they will cooperate and allow their children to attend these NFSs.

Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that Mosque, guesthouses and FSs in the evening shift as ESs may be used as NFSs in the province. Mosques and guesthouses can be used as NFSs in the locality. People of the area are very generous, cooperative and have special love for education so they can even dedicate their own houses for these NFSs. Likewise, the findings elaborated that FSs may be opened in the evening shift as NFSs for those children who work in the labour market at daytime.

DISCUSSION

The literacy rate in Afghanistan is not satisfactory. It is below the halfway around (UNICEF, 2021; UIL, 2020, CSRS, 2019). Moreover, the threatening news is that a great portion of the school-age-children i.e., 4 million children are out-of-schools in the country (UNICEF, 2021; Rescure.org, 2021; Beteille et al., 2020; World Bank Report, 2020; REUTERS, 2018). Several causes such as wars in the country, poverty, shortage of

schools' infrastructure, cultural norms and illiteracy of parents have contributed to the low literacy rate in the country (Kerawala, 2021; Menteş & Talas, 2021; Daud, 2020; Noori, 2017; Khwajamir, 2016; EFA, 2015). To cater to the low literacy rate in the country, NFSs are essential. NFSs for its flexibility and cost-effectiveness have been proven effective in the provision of basic education and alleviating illiteracy in areas where children do not have access to FSs due to various obstacles (Gul & Sarwar, 2020; Mbilu, 2019; Yasunaga, 2014). So, the current study investigated the feasibility of opening NFSs in Kunar province of Afghanistan. The study specifically investigated the educational accessibility gap, the need for opening NFSs and the possible strategies for opening NFSs in Kunar province of Afghanistan.

The study indicated that NFSs are feasible in Kunar province of Afghanistan. NFSs are feasible in Kunar province of Afghanistan because the current number of FSs in Kunar province are not enough. Similarly, there is a great number of out-of-school children in the province. This was confirmed by KDoE (2022) and Afzali (2018) who state that around 88 thousands of school-age-children are still out of schools in Kunar province of Afghanistan.

Similarly, there is a great need for the establishment of NFSs in the province and the idea of establishing NFSs in the province was warmly welcomed in the province. This further approve the feasibility of NFSs in the province. NFSs have been proven effective in the provision of basic education for its diversity and flexibility in conditions where children could not make to FSs due to different obstacles (Gul & Sarwar, 2020; Mbilu, 2019; Yasunaga, 2014). Many developing countries such as Bangladesh, Ghana and Uganda have established NFSs to achieve the goal of Education for All (EFA) and have particularly yielded significant results (Mbilu, 2019).

Moreover, several ways of establishing NFSs in the province were identified that ensure the feasibility of the NFSs in the province. Mosque, guesthouses and FSs in the evening shift are identified some of the possible ways to establish NFSs in the province. Mosques have been proven effective in the provision of basic education in the community. Mosque school for the provision of modern education is the best alternate option and the need of the day (Saeed et al., 2016). Furthermore, FSs may be opened as NFSs in the evening shift to enrol those children who work in the labour market at daytime. Evening schools provide study opportunities for those who are busy at daytime and because of their flexibility they are effective too (Luka et al., 2015). Around 2.5 million school-age-children (ages 6-14) in Afghanistan are working in labour market (UNICEF, 2018). So, to cater to the issue and provide those 2.5 million children with the opportunity of education, ESs are essential.

CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that opening NFSs are feasible in Kunar province of Afghanistan because there is an educational accessibility gap in the province i.e., the current number of FSs is insufficient and a large number of school-age-children are out-of-school in the province. Hard to access areas, Government limited resources, absence of nearby

schools, limited resources of the existing FSs, parents' economic issues and obstacles in the way of children to schools are some of the main reasons that have resulted educational accessibility gap in the province. Moreover, the study concluded that NFSs are feasible in Kunar province of Afghanistan because there is a great need for opening NFSs in the province as they are cost-effective, and the people of the province have positive attitudes towards opening NFSs in Kunar province. Furthermore, the study concluded that the NFSs are feasible in Kunar province of Afghanistan because Mosques and guesthouses in the community and FSs in the evening shift for those who work at daytime are the potential ways to open NFSs in the province. The people of the province are very generous, cooperative and have special love for education. They promised to dedicate their own houses for these NFSs. Likewise, officials in the DoE ensured that FSs may be opened in the evening shift as ESs to enrol those children who work in the labour market at daytime. So, opening FSs in the evening shift will provide them with the opportunity to study at the evening.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study the following recommendations were reached.

- The study found that the current number of primary schools in Kunar Province is insufficient because it is a mountainous province and most of the villages are distantly located from one another making it difficult for the government to establish FSs in every village; so, it is recommended to the Ministry of Education (MoE), Afghanistan to establish NFS system in the existing setup of Mosques, guesthouses and ESs for its cost-effectiveness.
- The study found that there is a great need for opening NFSs in the province and opening these NFSs are feasible in the existing setup of Mosques, guesthouses and FSs in the evening shift as ESs; so, it is recommended to the MoE, Afghanistan to take practical strides for opening these NFSs in the province and to bring all out-of-school children into schools and ultimately alleviate illiteracy.

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